

StreetVibes: An Open, Modular Pipeline for Reproducible Street-Level Urban Perception Analysis

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Summary

StreetVibes is an open-source, command-line Python library for automated urban perception analysis. By orchestrating OpenStreetMap, Mapillary, and locally hosted vision-language models (e.g., LLaVA and Llama), it enables street-level queries to be converted into semantic summaries and structured indicators of urban characteristics. The package lowers the technical barrier to integrating generative AI into geospatial workflows, providing an end-to-end, free, and privacy-preserving alternative to commercial APIs for qualitative urban analytics. We discuss key limitations related to data availability, external dependencies, and model bias to contextualise appropriate use of the package.

KEYWORDS: Urban Perception, Generative AI, Vision-Language Models, Open Source Software, Reproducibility

1 Introduction

Street-level imagery has become a core data source for urban analytics in GIS, yet the field is constrained by dependence on proprietary platforms (especially Google Street View¹), weak reproducibility, licensing issues, and uneven access to imagery, driving interest towards open, crowd-sourced alternatives such as Mapillary (Biljecki and Ito, 2021).

Vision-Language Models (VLMs), including contrastively trained CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pre-training) (Radford et al., 2021), expand what can be inferred from street imagery to cover subjective phenomena such as walkability (Liu et al., 2023), street safety (Wang et al., 2025) and even user-oriented photo tagging intent (Ilyankou et al., 2026); UrbanCLIP² demonstrates that careful prompt and label-space engineering can turn a pretrained VLM into a zero-shot urban

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¹<https://www.google.com/streetview/>

²<https://github.com/RightBank/UrbanCLIP>

function classifier with strong cross-city transfer (Huang et al., 2024). Multimodal Large Language Models (LLMs) have been used to estimate subjective perceptions such as safety (Zhang et al., 2025), and to surface how those judgements shift under different implied observers via persona prompting (Beneduce et al., 2025). Comparative work also tests whether VLM-generated perceptual ratings can approximate human evaluations, pointing to practical routes for scaling perceptual audits (Moreno-Vera and POCO, 2025). Meanwhile, open software packages such as ZenSVI (Ito et al., 2025) or OpenFACADES (Liang et al., 2025) standardise acquisition and processing of street-view imagery into reproducible pipelines for urban analysis.

However, there is still a usability gap as pipelines assume substantial engineering effort or access to paid commercial APIs. StreetVibes targets this gap with a street-name-first command-line interface (CLI) and a lightweight, transparent, end-to-end pipeline that orchestrates OpenStreetMap (OSM) geocoding and geometry retrieval, Mapillary image sampling, and locally run, swappable VLMs and LLMs. The result is a low-friction route from a named street to interpretable summaries and task-specific metrics, designed to make generative-AI street-view analysis reproducible, customisable, and practically deployable in everyday GIS workflows. We release the package on GitHub³ under the MIT license.

2 Python package

StreetVibes is designed as an end-to-end, command-line-driven Python package. The pipeline’s components are illustrated in Figure 1. The package requires Ollama⁴ to be installed and running locally, with the relevant models pulled in advance; this is a one-time setup step documented in the package README⁵.

The single required input is a street name, which is geocoded using OSM’s Nominatim⁶. The corresponding street geometry is retrieved via the Overpass API⁷ and sampled proportionally along its length. By default, $n = 5$ points are sampled. For each sampled point, the pipeline queries Mapillary⁸ to retrieve nearby image(s) (default = 1 per point), requiring a free, user-provided Mapillary API token. By default, we pick the most recent image within ± 0.0002 degrees of the sampled point.

Each image is analysed by a VLM, which is prompted (by default) to produce concise descriptions focusing on walkability, traffic, greenery, safety, and socio-economic cues from an urban planning perspective. The resulting image-level descriptions are then passed to an LLM, which synthesises them into a single street-level summary. Output is structured as JSON by default, with configurable keys. Both vision and summary prompts are customisable.

By default, the package uses locally hosted Ollama models, specifically LLaVA⁹ for vision and

³<https://github.com/ilyankou/streetvibes>

⁴<https://ollama.com/download>

⁵<https://github.com/ilyankou/streetvibes/blob/main/README.md>

⁶<https://nominatim.org/>

⁷<https://overpass-api.de/>

⁸<https://www.mapillary.com/>

⁹<https://ollama.com/library/llava>

Figure 1: Overview of the StreetVibes pipeline. A street name is geocoded using OSM (Nominatim), geometry is retrieved via Overpass, points are sampled along the street, nearby Mapillary images are queried, image-level descriptions are generated by a VLM and synthesised into a street-level summary by an LLM.

Llama-3.1¹⁰ for text synthesis.

Table 1 summarises command-line arguments controlling the package’s behaviour. The positional argument `location` is required; all other arguments are optional.

Figure 2 shows the interface and the output for the query ‘shoot-up hill, london’.

3 Potential applications

StreetVibes is intended for exploratory street-level analysis and methodological experimentation for prompt-driven assessment of perceptual attributes such as scenic-ness or walkability. For example, a local authority might screen hundreds of streets for pedestrian infrastructure quality before prioritising maintenance budgets without manual site visits; a planning consultancy might compare perceived safety and socio-economic cues across candidate development sites; or a researcher might test whether prompt wording or model choice systematically shifts perceived safety scores across neighbourhoods, using StreetVibes as a controlled experimental framework.

The package can also be used to examine qualitative alignment between model-generated street assessments and external spatial datasets (e.g. vegetation indices, road classifications), and to study the sensitivity of urban perception outputs to prompt design, model choice, and spatial aggregation. More broadly, StreetVibes provides a lightweight mechanism for integrating generative

¹⁰<https://ollama.com/library/llama3.1>

Table 1: Core command-line arguments for StreetVibes and their default values. The positional argument location is required; all others are optional.

Argument	Default	Description
location	–	Target location or street identifier
--points	5	Number of points sampled along the street
--per-point	1	Number of images per sampled point
--dir	street_images	Output directory for saved images
--v-model	llava	Vision model used via Ollama
--v-prompt	None	Custom prompt for the vision model (uses built-in prompt if unset)
--t-model	llama3.1	Text model used via Ollama
--t-prompt	None	Custom prompt for the text model (uses built-in prompt if unset)
--structured	True	Return structured JSON output
--json-keys	‘summary, land_use, walkability, traffic, greenery, safety, maintenance, socio-economic, variations’	JSON keys for structured output

intuitive street extent, possibly due to fragmented OSM geometries, pedestrian-only segments, or adjacent way merges. Greenness scores range from 2 to 6; streets bordering formal green spaces or containing mature street trees (e.g. Bloomsbury Square and Bloomsbury Way) receive higher greenness scores (mean index = 6), while streets dominated by dense built form and limited roadside planting (e.g. Southampton Row) receive lower scores (mean index = 2). This generally corresponds to the ground truth data shown in Figure 3. Most streets cluster around moderate values (3-4), consistent with the mixed business, residential, and institutional character of the study area.

4 Limitations

The primary limitation of the pipeline is the availability and quality of street-level imagery. Mapillary coverage is uneven and strongly biased towards central and well-travelled areas; for peripheral neighbourhoods, imagery is often sparse, outdated, or of poor visual quality, which constrains spatial coverage and output reliability.

The pipeline depends on Nominatim and Overpass APIs; both are free, established, and well-documented, but are occasionally unavailable or unresponsive due to rate limits and intermittent downtime, which can prevent retrieval of street geometries and disrupt automated runs.

Geocoding in particular introduces an additional source of error. Street names are not always uniquely or correctly resolved by the Nominatim geocoder, especially in cases of common names, informal naming, or complex street geometries, potentially leading to incorrect spatial queries.

Streets provide an intuitive unit of analysis but may not be the most appropriate spatial scale for urban perception. Perceptual characteristics can vary within and across streets and may align more

#	Street	OSM ID	Captured length (m)	Approx. ref. length (m)	Images retrieved	Greenness index (1–10)
1	Great Russell Street	2876427	541	540	5	4
2	Bloomsbury Square	438309961	337	310	5	6
3	Southampton Row	438311806	310	350	4	2
4	Vernon Place	4236993	116	60	5	4
5	Bloomsbury Way	741348615	301	280	5	6
6	Bury Place	438304614	118	200	5	4
7	Little Russell Street	67551928	168	170	3	4
8	Museum Street	1447983649	252	250	4	3
9	Coptic Street	4615507	57	110	3	4
10	Streatham Street	67551930	53	120	3	4
11	Bloomsbury Street	694567131	124	210	5	4
12	Willoughby Street	4253554	54	50	3	3
13	Gilbert Place	4253215	114	110	4	4
14	Bloomsbury Place	3088166	61	60	4	4

Table 2: Street-level greenness results for the Bloomsbury case study. OSM IDs are the first matched segment of the street name. Captured length represents the entire captured street segment, including the referenced and adjacent OSM ways. Reference length is approximate and is measured in Google Maps. Fewer images than sampled points indicate unavailable Mapillary imagery.

naturally with alternative units such as blocks or neighbourhoods, motivating further exploration of different kinds of aggregation.

Model-based interpretation introduces systematic biases (Manvi et al., 2024). VLMs operate on individual images captured at specific moments; bad weather, lighting conditions, or transient events such as rush-hour traffic or construction activity may result in assessments that are not representative of typical street conditions. More generally, both vision and language models reflect biases in their training data, which may influence how urban features are perceived and described, including documented geographic imbalances in large-scale web corpora (Ilyankou et al., 2024).

Our method samples a number of points per street and relies on nearest-image retrieval, which may not capture within-street heterogeneity, particularly for long or visually diverse streets.

Beyond technical limitations, long-term maintenance is not guaranteed, though the MIT licence of our package permits community forking and continued development.

5 Conclusion

StreetVibes provides a lightweight, CLI-driven approach for integrating street-level imagery, open geospatial data, and locally hosted vision–language models to support exploratory urban perception analysis. By exposing a configurable end-to-end pipeline, the package enables transparent and reproducible experimentation with qualitative street assessments while avoiding reliance on propri-

Figure 3: Green cover in the Bloomsbury study area (September 2024), used as contextual reference for validating street-level greenness scores. Source: Mayor of London City Intelligence (<https://apps.london.gov.uk/green-cover/?layers=green>). Contains OS data © Crown copyright and database.

etary APIs. While our approach is constrained by data availability, external service dependencies, and model bias, it offers a practical foundation for rapid prototyping and methodological exploration at the intersection of geospatial analysis and generative AI.

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Biography

Ilya Ilyankou is a third-year PhD student at University College London (UCL). His research focuses on mapping natural-language intent onto structured geospatial data. He uses crowdsourced data and street-level imagery to quantify spatial intent, salience, and say-do gaps, and to translate these into design requirements for geospatial systems, with applications in perception-aware routing and large-scale geographic concept extraction.

Dr Stefano Cavazzi is a Principal Innovation and Research Scientist at Ordnance Survey (OS), with 15 years of experience in geospatial data integration, applied AI, and national infrastructure mapping.

Dr James Haworth is Associate Professor in Spatio-temporal Analytics at University College London (UCL). His research focuses on machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques for spatiotemporal data modelling and analysis, with applications in transportation, geodemographics and crime, amongst others.

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